

Initial DataOps Architecture for 6G-DALI

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Abstract—A novel DataOps architecture is proposed under the 6G-DALI (6G Data and ML operations automation via an end-to-end AI framework) project to enable intelligent, user-driven data management across dynamic 6G environments. The framework leverages Large Language Models (LLMs), automated ELT pipelines, and secure federated services to orchestrate the retrieval, generation, transformation, and governance of both pre-existing (“cold”) and on-demand (“hot”) datasets. Together, these components establish a scalable and transparent foundation for AI-driven, high-quality, and on-demand data engineering in future 6G systems.

Index Terms—DataOps, ELT, Dataspace

I. INTRODUCTION

The 6G-DALI (6G Data and ML operations automation via an end-to-end AI framework) initiative introduces a novel DataOps architecture designed to fulfill user-driven requests for data in highly dynamic and federated environments. The core objective of the architecture is to provide seamless access to datasets for reuse or further transformation and to manage their end-to-end lifecycle through automated, intelligent data engineering pipelines. These datasets could be either pre-processed datasets available in the 6G-DALI Dataspace, which are called “cold data”, or datasets generated on-demand from distributed testbeds, which are called “hot data”.

II. DATAOPS ARCHITECTURE

The architecture, as depicted in Figure 1, integrates an array of interoperable components that collectively orchestrate the retrieval, generation, transformation, and governance of datasets. The 6G-DALI framework includes a user interface that facilitates user interaction, enabling experimenters to express data requests in natural language. These user intents are interpreted by integrated Large Language Model (LLM) systems, which translate them into search queries compatible with the 6G Dataspace Catalogue or into executable experiment descriptions to enable automated testbed utilization when the required datasets do not yet exist in the Dataspace and has to be generated. An IDS Connector [1] is also part of the framework so that it can interact with the 6G Dataspace to query the catalogue and testbeds to extract data.

To support dynamic experimentation, the 6G-DALI framework includes a Testbed Selection System, which employs intelligent algorithms to identify the most suitable testbed based on user needs and resource availability. The testbeds, where data generation experiments take place, are equipped with Adapters (IDS Connectors) to interact securely with the framework to receive experiment requests and with the

Dataspace to publish metadata of the generated datasets. Upon data retrieval or generation, ELT (Extract, Load, Transform) pipelines are triggered automatically. These pipelines include data cleansing and augmentation mechanisms to ensure data quality, complemented by performance and quality indicators for dataset assessment. The transformation services are executed in an internal environment provided by the framework. After processing, datasets generated on-demand are stored in the 6G Dataspace which enables secure and scalable data exchange. It includes a Metadata Broker, that facilitates the exchange of metadata between participants in the Dataspace. An Identity Provider, which is a service responsible for user authentication that ensures only authorized entities can access data and services. A Clearing House that ensures safe exchange of data between participants by managing contacts, pricing and ensuring both parties adhere to agreed-upon conditions. Finally, a Federated Catalogue, a repository that exposes metadata about the available datasets as well as available transformation services including data augmentation and data cleaning techniques.

III. CONCLUSION

To sum up, the 6G-DALI DataOps architecture provides a foundational layer for federated, AI-driven, and on-demand data engineering in 6G environments. By integrating intelligent user interaction, automated ELT processes, and coordinated testbed operations, it lays the groundwork for scalable, transparent, and high-quality data access for future 6G applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] International Data Spaces Association, “IDS Reference Architecture Model 4.0,” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://internationaldataspaces.org/publications/>

Fig. 1. 6G-DALI Initial DataOps Architecture